

Literature Review on PPG-First, ECG-First, and Motion-Tracking-First Devices

This section evaluates wearable devices for the three measurement techniques retained as candidates for the data pipeline (photoplethysmography (PPG), electrocardiography (ECG) and motion tracking via inertial measurement units (IMUs) and accelerometers). The three subsections each open with a description of the corresponding technique before evaluating the relevant devices in detail.

1. PPG-First Devices

PPG is frequently used for non-invasive measurements performed at the skin surface as it is “a simple and low-cost optical technique that can be used to detect blood volume changes in the microvascular bed of tissue” (Allen, 2007, p. 1). More specifically, a light source illuminates the skin, and a photodetector captures intensity variations caused by changes in blood perfusion within the tissue volume. PPG signals then form a photoplethysmogram waveform in which each pulse corresponds to a heartbeat. By identifying successive pulse peaks, the time between beats can be extracted (Brunzini et al., 2021). HR is then calculated from the frequency of these pulses, expressed in beats per minute.

Importantly, according to Li et al. (2023), the accuracy of PPG based measurements is not consistently reliable in an industrial context. The quality of PPG measurements depends on consistent contact between the device and the skin. Particularly during periods of intense movement, maintaining this contact can be difficult. In addition, sweat may influence the accuracy of the PPG signal. This presents a fundamental limitation of PPG-based wearables under the data accuracy criterion, which prevents any of them from being rated high on this criterion in Table 1. *Overview of All Assessed Wearable Devices 1.*

Empatica E4 and EmbracePlus

Existing research into worker’s physiological features often uses the Empatica E4 wristband, an easy-to-use wearable that is medically graded for accurate physiological measurements (Brunzini et al., 2021; Hijry et al., 2024). The device’s PPG sensor measures HR. HRV can be calculated using additional software such as Kubios HRV Standard (Brunzini et al., 2021). It supports wireless connectivity and real-time data streaming, and includes onboard storage capabilities (Hijry et al., 2024). The wristband also has an electrodermal activity sensor (EDA) and a 3-axis accelerometer.

However, the Empatica E4 has now been discontinued and replaced by its successor, the Empatica EmbracePlus (Empatica Inc., 2026). While this device upgrades some of the original features, still has medical grade accuracy, and remains easy to wear, it does not support real-time data streaming or access, nor does it provide an SDK (Empatica Inc., 2026). Nevertheless, the device has been used in literature by Morillo et al. (2026).

Furthermore, with a mandatory data subscription raising the total cost to €1998, the device is not cost-effective for large-scale Industry 5.0 deployment (Empatica Inc., 2026).

Considering the limitations for the data access and the cost-effectiveness criteria, the EmbracePlus is not regarded as a viable option for further consideration in this research.

Polar OH1

Other research has used the Polar OH1 to track HR in lab and field settings (Hettiarachchi et al., 2019). The Polar OH1 provides HR measurements based on PPG. It is primarily designed to be worn around the (fore)arm, and can be done so in a comfortable and non-intrusive way.

Polar provides an SDK to support data access (Polar Electro, 2025), but notes that the OH1 does not provide real-time HRV data during exercise and points to the H10 ECG chest band as a more suitable option for HRV tracking (Polar Electro, 2026b).

It is available from the manufacturer for approx. €35 (Polar Electro, 2026b).

Its limitations under the data accuracy and real-time availability of real-time HRV data, combined with the availability of a more suitable alternative, result in the OH1 not being considered a viable option for this research.

Other PPG Wearables

Across different studies, a plethora of wrist worn consumer-focused lifestyle and sports trackers have been used for PPG derived HR(V) measurements. Examples are the Apple Watch (O'Grady et al., 2024), Whoop Band (Van Oost et al., 2025), Microsoft Band (Lee et al., 2019), Garmin Fenix (Dial et al., 2025), Fitbit Charge (Natarajan et al., 2020), and Versa (Nasr et al., 2025). Furthermore, finger worn rings from the brand Oura (Dial et al., 2025; Li et al., 2023) have also frequently been used for PPG derived HR(V) measurements in the past. However, these devices generally do not offer direct access to raw PPG data. The signals are preprocessed and made available only through proprietary applications, limiting the possibility of developing a comprehensive end-to-end data pipeline. The latter allows us to stop further analysis into these wearables altogether.

2. ECG-First Devices

ECG is a measurement method used to record the heart's electrical activity and rhythm (Loizaga et al., 2023). An ECG monitors cardiac activity by capturing physiological electrical signals via sensors placed on the skin (leads) that are wired directly to an ECG machine (Johns Hopkins Medicine, 2025). Standard ECG setups utilize 12 leads to capture the electrical phases of the cardiac cycle. This cycle consists of segmented waves, including the QRS complex (Loizaga et al., 2023). The maximum amplitude of the R wave within this cycle is called the R-peak. The temporal distance between consecutive R-peaks forms the RR-interval, which is a typically used metric to calculate HR and HRV.

Nowadays, there are increasingly popular wearable ECG devices that use far fewer leads than 12 (often even single-lead), but still produce reliable data, while remaining comfortable to wear and move in (Neri et al., 2024). Since, in this research, the focus is on devices that can be easily used in an industrial setting, we will focus on this category.

Polar H10

The Polar H10 is arguably the most widely used single-lead wearable ECG device. It uses an easy-to-wear chest strap (Polar Electro, 2026a). In addition, the chest band also captures accelerometer data. Extensive research has confirmed that the Polar H10 provides highly accurate HR measurements (Dial et al., 2025; Gilgen-Ammann et al., 2019; O'Grady et al., 2024; Skála et al., 2022; Speer et al., 2020; Villani et al., 2022).

Polar provides an SDK that allows real-time ECG data access, allowing researchers to work directly with the raw data (Polar Electro, 2025). However, this SDK is primarily designed for mobile application development, which may limit direct integration into a custom end-to-end data pipeline. Third-party Python libraries (e.g., Polar-Python, which interfaces via Bluetooth Low Energy using Bleak (Zhe_learn, 2025)) offer potential alternatives for integration, albeit with limitations regarding official support.

The H10 is available from the manufacturer for approx. €100 (Polar Electro, 2026a).

In conclusion, the Polar H10 performs strongly across all the defined evaluation criteria and is a viable option for this research.

Movesense Wearables

Different researchers have also validated the accuracy of Movesense’s MD (Rogers et al., 2022) and HR+ (Martín Gómez et al., 2024) single-lead ECG sensor device. These are designed to be worn on a chest strap, similar to the Polar H10, and are thus non-intrusive. They were shown to be close in accuracy to more traditional ECG monitors. Furthermore, the Movesense HR2 is identical to the HR+ in terms of ECG specifications, differing only by the inclusion of an internal temperature sensor, which is not relevant for the purposes of this research (Figure 1). Additionally, these devices come with 9-axis IMU (3x accelerometer, 3x gyroscope, 3x magnetometer).

Figure 1.

Movesense Sensor Information. Source: Provided by Movesense via Personal Communication (email), January 2026.

	Movesense HR2	Movesense HR+	Movesense Flash	Movesense MD
Class IIa medical device (MDR)				X
9-axis motion sensor: accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer	X	X	X	X
Heart rate, R-R intervals, BLE heart rate service	X	X	X	X
1-channel ECG bandwidth	10Hz - 34Hz	10Hz - 34Hz	0.5Hz - 40Hz	0.5Hz - 40Hz
1-wire expansion bus		X		
Temperature		X	X	X (non-medical)
Data logging memory	384kB	384kB	128MB	384kB
Developer tools for firmware customization	X	X	X	X
Memory for custom applications	X	X	X	X
Bluetooth® Smart radio for data transfer	X	X	X	X
Mobile libraries for iOS and Android	X	X	X	X
Water resistance	30m/100ft	30m/100ft	30m/100ft	30m/100ft

Movesense offers an official Python client designed to facilitate automated and customizable data collection (Movesense Ltd., 2025). It is based on the GATT SensorData Protocol (GSP) and supports access to all physiological data recorded by the sensor in real time. According to Movesense itself, “the Python client is a perfect solution for data pipelines”.

These devices are available from €349 (MD), €119 (HR+), and €99 (HR2), making especially the HR+ and HR2 attractive options (Movesense Ltd., n.d.).

In conclusion, the Movesense HR+ and HR2 sensors perform well across all evaluation criteria. In particular, the availability of an official Python client strongly supports seamless integration into a real-time data pipeline, distinguishing them from other alternatives.

Other ECG Wearables

An accurate alternative would be Zephyr’s BioHarness 3.0. This is a single-lead, easy-to-wear, chest-worn ECG (Van Oost et al., 2025, p. 3). However, the BioHarness 3.0 is available from €765 and upwards (HaB International Ltd., 2026), making it too expensive to be widely deployed in an Industry 5.0 setting.

Another single-lead wearable in-garment, and thus non-intrusive, ECG monitor used in a recent study is the YouCare device (Neri et al., 2024). The data quality obtained from the device was comparable to data from a conventional Holter monitor. However, information on the real-time accessibility of data and the price has not yet been released.

The Smartex Wearable Wellness System is another wearable in-garment, and thus non-intrusive, ECG monitor that can be used for the tracking of physiological conditions (Donati et al., 2023). The device combines its single-lead ECG with a piezoelectric band to measure the extension of the ribcage during breathing, and a 9-axis IMU (Smartex, 2022). Even though this device seems to provide a set of useful datapoints, there is no literature available assessing its data quality. Furthermore, the device comes with an SDK (Donati et al., 2023), which supports the integration into the pipeline. Unfortunately, this device is not yet available for purchase, and thus the price remains unknown.

More options are available on the market, like the Equivital EQ02(+) and QardioCore chest strap. However, like some of the previously mentioned options, these are rather expensive with price points as high as €1940 (MindTecStore, n.d.) and €499 (Qardio, 2025), respectively, making them unattractive options.

3. Motion-Tracking-First Devices

To capture motion- and acceleration-based indicators of fatigue, wearable inertial sensors offer a practical and non-intrusive solution (Sedighi Maman et al., 2017). Motion-tracking devices can provide detailed, continuous information on human movement patterns during work tasks. Examples of motion tracking devices are IMUs and accelerometers. IMUs typically integrate a 3-axis accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer, enabling the extraction of rich kinematic features, whereas simpler accelerometers focus solely on linear acceleration (Ferrete Ribeiro & Santos, 2017).

The predictive performance of motion-tracking systems is influenced by sensor placement. Using IMUs on multiple body segments can improve fatigue detection by capturing movement patterns from different parts of the body during physically demanding tasks (Sedighi Maman et al., 2017).

Shimmer3

Shimmer3 is commonly used in human motion analysis research (Bosio et al., 2025; Sedighi Maman et al., 2017). They integrate a 3-axis accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer. The Shimmer3 units are compact (51 mm × 34 mm × 14 mm), lightweight, and designed for wearable use (Leone et al., 2023). They provide adequate acceleration measurements for wearable motion analysis, although their accuracy and consistency are lower than those of some higher-end research IMUs (Bosio et al., 2025).

Shimmer3 devices support wireless real-time transmission via a low-power Bluetooth connection (Leone et al., 2023; Sedighi Maman et al., 2017). Furthermore, development kits and open-source software are provided (Shimmer Research Ltd., 2026).

Their small form factor limits the physical burden on the operator (Leone et al., 2023), making them suitable for long-term physical fatigue monitoring in industrial settings.

Regarding the cost, a single Shimmer3 IMU costs approximately €430. However, a Consensys development kit is required for data collection, increasing the minimum price to €598, with costs rising further depending on the number of units purchased (Shimmer Research Ltd., 2026).

Despite strong performance, the Shimmer3's high base cost, which increases further with additional sensors, limits scalability, and makes it unsuitable for this research.

HTC Vive Trackers

Motion tracking can also be performed using HTC Vive Trackers 3.0. They function as small, wearable motion-capture units that can be attached to a body segment using straps (Brunzini et al., 2021). Each

tracker determines its 3D position by detecting infrared signals from fixed base stations, enabling real-time tracking of body part movement. In their setup, multiple trackers were used. This allowed reconstruction of full-body posture during manual tasks (Brunzini et al., 2021). The HTC Vive Tracker 3.0 provides centimeter-level positional accuracy that is sufficient for real-time motion tracking (Merker et al., 2023).

These positional data were streamed through Steam VR into the XRErgo software environment (Brunzini et al., 2021). As Vive Trackers work with infrared signals, they depend on a controlled indoor environment with correctly placed base stations, limiting their practicality in dynamic industrial settings.

A single tracker costs approx. €149 and a base station costs approx. €245 (HTC Corporation, 2026).

While the Vive Trackers provide accurate motion data and real-time posture monitoring, their reliance on multiple body-mounted units and infrared base stations introduces practical constraints that may limit their suitability in highly dynamic industrial environments.

Table 1.*Overview of All Assessed Wearable Devices*

Device Name	Type	Accurate Data	Access to Real-Time Data	Industrially Suitable		Cost Effective	Literature
				Accurate Data	Access to Real-Time Data		
Empatica E4/ Embrace Plus	PPG	Medium	No	Yes	No		Brunzini et al. (2021), Hijry et al. (2024), Morillo et al. (2026), Empatica Inc. (2026)
Polar OH1	PPG	Medium	No	Yes	Yes		Hettiarachchi et al. (2019), Polar Electro (2025), Polar Electro (2026b)
Other Consumer PPG Wearables	PPG	Medium	No	Yes	Device Dependent		O'Grady et al. (2024), Van Oost et al. (2025), Lee et al. (2019), Dial et al. (2025), Natarajan et al. (2020), Nasr et al. (2025), Li et al. (2023)
Polar H10	ECG	High	Yes	Yes	Yes		Gilgen-Ammann et al. (2019), Skála et al. (2022), Speer et al. (2020), Dial et al. (2025), O'Grady et al. (2024), Villani et al. (2022), Polar Electro (2025), Polar Electro (2026a), Zhe_learn (2025)
Movesense MD	ECG	High	Yes	Yes	No		Rogers et al. (2022), Movesense Ltd. (2025), Movesense Ltd. (n.d.)
Movesense HR+/HR2	ECG	High	Yes	Yes	Yes		Martin Gómez et al. (2024), Movesense Ltd. (2025), Movesense Ltd. (n.d.)
Zephyr BioHarness 3.0	ECG	High	Unknown	Yes	No		Van Oost et al. (2025), HaB International Ltd. (2026)
YouCare	ECG	High	No	Yes	Unknown		Neri et al. (2024)
Smartex Wearable Wellness System	ECG	Unknown	Yes	Yes	Unknown		Donati et al. (2023), Smartex (2025)
Shimmer3 IMU	IMU	Medium	Yes	Yes	No		Bosio et al. (2025), Leone et al. (2023), Sedighi Maman et al. (2017), Shimmer Research Ltd. (2026)
HTC Vive Trackers	Motion Tracking	Medium	Yes	No	No		Brunzini et al. (2021), Merker et al. (2023), HTC Corporation (2026)

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